

The Analysis of Imperative Speech Acts of Translation Strategy in Subtitle Serial Squid Game (Episode 1)

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ABSTRACT: Lately, broadcasts from South Korea have been in great demand in the world, including Indonesia. These shows can be in the form of videos, films, serials and dramas. A presentation displays the behavior or action conveyed through communication between the speaker (speaker) and the listener (opposite), which is referred to as a speech act. One type of speech act is imperative speech act. An imperative speech act is a form of speech in which the speaker demands action from the listener. To understand the broadcast, it through the translation results which are displayed in the form of subtitles. There are many translation strategies that can be used, not only literal strategies, to do the translation. This study aims 1) to reveal translation strategies used to translate imperative utterances in Squid Game episode 1, and 2) to analyze the types of translation strategies used to translate imperative utterances in Squid Game episode 1 dialogue series. This research used descriptive qualitative method. Speech data and translation results were collected through the Language Reactor and analyzed using Salihien Moentaha's translation strategy theory. The results showed that there were 53 direct imperative utterances found. From the translation of the speech, 8 types of translation strategies were found, namely Literal (23 times), Free Translation (6 times), Paraphrasing (12 times), Replacement (3 times) with word class types (1 time) and replacement of part of the sentence with active operations types. -passive (2 times), Lexical replacement (12 times) with the type of concretization (2 times); Generalization (3 times); Antonym (2 times); Compensation (2 times), Addition (17 Times), Omission (8 Times), Compression (27 Times), Explication (2 Times). The most dominant translation strategy used is the Compression strategy.

KEYWORDS: Imperatives, Korean, Semantics, Speech Acts, Translation Strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

As technology advances, it is very easy for people to get entertainment shows from various countries, one of which is the Squid Game series from South Korea which was trending in 2021. This Korean series of course includes various translations of subtitles so that foreign viewers from various countries can understand the storyline of the film. One of them is a Indonesian translation.

Subtitle is the delivery of dialogue in the form of text on a display which is usually displayed at the bottom of the screen to convey dialogue in the target language from the source language. The process of making subtitles is called subtitling. Hidayatullah, (2019) argued that subtitles must use language that is short, concise, and precise in meaning because when watching a film, of course, there are many scenes or scenes that alternate quickly so that the audience must be quick to read and understand the subtitles.

The subtitles usually show the translation results from the Source Language (SL) into the Target Language (BSa). According to Nida and Taber (1969), translating means creating the closest equivalent to the SL to the message from SL. The closest equivalent is first in terms of meaning and second in style.

Furthermore, the form of speech has a peculiarity in that the listener has almost no choice either to accept or reject the utterance, so it can be said that the imperative form of speech makes the speaker appear to have high authority which makes the listener do nothing but act based on what the speaker said (Bayat, 2013).

Therefore, the researcher is interested in analyzing imperative speech acts translation strategies in the Squid Game series subtitles (episode 1). This study aims to identify the translation strategies used in translating imperative speech acts in the subtitles of the Squid Game episode 1 series as well as the dominant translation strategies used and their causes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

a. Culture

Culture is the characteristics and knowledge of a particular group of people, including language, religion, cuisine, social customs,

music and art, It is the social behavior and norms found in human society (Andini et al., 2021). Moreover, culture is considered a central concept in anthropology, encompassing various phenomena that are transmitted through social learning in society (Jariah et al., 2022; Rahman et al., 2022). Universal culture is found in all societies; this includes expressive forms such as art, music, dance, rituals in the sense of customs, religion, and technology such as the use of tools, cooking, shelter, and clothing (Weda et al., 2022; Dalyan et al., 2022).

b. Translation

Translation is the transfer of thoughts or ideas from one source language into another (Rahman et al., 2019; Sahib et al., 2019). Furthermore, translation is changing the text of the source language into the text of the target language by considering the meanings of the two languages so that they are tried to be as similar as possible, what is equally important is that the translation must follow the rules that apply in the target language (Rahman & Letlora, 2018).

c. Translation Process

The process of translation cause a various kinds of translation techniques or strategies that can be used to translate the meaning of a sentence (Nurhayati, 2017; Moentaha, 2008) even said that there are 11 types of translation strategies, which are as follows:

1. Literal translation (literal translation) is translate words according to their literal meaning or their original meaning in the dictionary.

2. Substitution (substitution) such literal but usually used to translate a term which has only one equivalent or one meaning

3. Free translation means it carried out at the level of the sentence or text as a whole, namely by providing an overview of the situation so as to produce an equivalent situation and not an equivalent meaning

4. Paraphrase (paraphrase) is same as free translation, but occurs at the word or phrase level

5. Replacements: replacement of grammatical units (word class, sentence parts), lexical units (certain words), and sentence constructions.

a) Replacing word classes, for example changing noun categories to verbs.

b) Replacement of parts of sentences, words in BSu do not have the same syntactic function when translated into BSa. (1) Changes in active-passive sentence structure, (2) subject change to description; time, place, and causation (causes).

c. Lexical replacement

(1) Concretization (from broad to narrow), the broad meaning in the source language is translated into a narrower meaning in the target language. (2) Generalization (from narrow to broad), the narrow meaning in the source language is translated into a broader meaning in the target language or using more general/neutral terms.

d. Antonymic translation

Replacing words in one language with their antonyms in another language by changing the news sentence into a denial sentence and vice versa.

e. Compensation

It was done due to the impossibility of conveying the information contained in BSu units to BSa units

6. Additions

Lexical additions or words without adding to the meaning in the SL

7. Omission/dropping

Removing abundant words because without those abundant words, the contents of information in SL texts can be fully conveyed into TL

8. Compression

Condensing linguistic elements into TL so that it is denser, shorter, and concise

9. Syntactic derivation Concerning active-passive operations, antonym translation, and conversion

10. Descriptive translation

Using a combination of free words by explaining lexical units that reflect the specific reality of one country or another, because there is no lexical equivalent.

11. Explication/implication

Realizing explicit disclosure in TL text, because there are implications in SL text information so that the disclosure is not clear,

and vice versa.

In a broadcast, of course there is a dialogue which contains speech acts. A speech act, 발화행위[balhwahaengwi] or 화행[hwahaeng] for short is an attitude what the speaker wants to show through communication (Koo et al., 2017). There are various types of speech acts, one of which is imperative speech acts.

Imperative speech acts are composed of imperative sentences. Lee (1998) stated that imperative sentences are sentences that express a relationship or connection between two parties due to an action between the speaker and the listener, so that the speaker demands the listener to take an action.

Most of the language learners themselves more often interpret a SL word or sentence directly or literally into TL because the strategy or technique of literal translation is an integral part of the translation process and is a basic strategy in translation so that it is often found using this strategy in the translation process (Arffman, 2012). Even though there are many strategies can be used to translate a word or sentence while maintaining the original meaning of the word or sentence itself, as seen in the dialogue example above. Each language also has its own language rules, so that in translation it is often difficult to adapt the translation from SL to TL.

III. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This study aims 1) to reveal translation strategies used to translate imperative utterances in Squid Game episode 1, and 2) to analyze the types of translation strategies used to translate imperative utterances in Squid Game episode 1 dialogue series.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In Squid Game episode 1, lasted for 60 minutes, 53 direct imperative utterances were found. By using Salihen Moentaha's translation strategy theory which contains 11 translation strategies, 8 types of translation strategies were found, namely as follows.

Table 1. Translation strategies found in subtitle translation of imperative speech acts in Squid Game episode 1 series

No.	Types of Translation Strategies	Amount	Data Number
1	Literally	23	2,6,7,8,11,12,15,16,17,19,21,24,27,30, 32,43,44,46,49,50,51,52,53
2	Substitution	0	-
3	Free translation	6	17,23,35,38,39,49
4	Paraphrase	12	1,6,14,18,22,31,37,40,43,46,47,50
5	Word Class Replacement	1	44
6	Active-Passive Part	2	12,27
7	Subject Sentence	0	-
8	Concrete Lexics	2	13,22
9	Generalization	3	3,7,53
10	Antonym	2	4,11
11	Compensation	2	15,17
12	Addition	17	2,3,4,6,8,15,19,21,22,36,37,41,44,45,48, 50,52
13	Disappearance	8	10,15,17,24,27,32,40, 43

For Syntactic Derivation, it includes active-passive operations, antonym translation, and conversion (change of word classes) so that it is considered 0. The most widely used or dominant translation strategy is Compression.

Of all the translation strategies used to translate imperative speech acts in the Squid Game episode 1 series, the type of translation strategy used most is Compression, which is 27 times. Based on the analysis, compression is the most widely used because utterances can be delivered in more concise expressions but still contain the same meaning. The use of this strategy is very supportive for subtitle translation, considering that when watching a broadcast, there are many alternating scenes so that the audience must be able to understand the contents of the film through subtitles and not instead be busy reading subtitles. The following is an example of using the compression strategy in translating imperative speech acts.

	Data 1 (Min 35:23)
BSu	너 일로 와 봐
	[nô illo wa bwa]
BSa	Come here

The utterance above is an imperative speech act marked by an ending imperative informal language variety 아/어[a/ô] attached to the phrase 와 봐[wa bwa].

The context of the speech above is as follows. The speech was spoken by Seong Gi Hun to Kang Sae Byeok, one of the participants in the game. Sae Byeok is a woman who accidentally gets hit by him when he tries to run away from a group of thugs. When they collided at that time, Sae Byeok secretly took the money from Gi Hun's horse race bet which fell so that Gi Hun could not pay off his debt to the group of thugs. This made Gi Hun furious and as soon as he saw Sae Byeok, he tried to make sure that it was Sae Byeok while saying the above in a tone full of emotion while clutching Sae Byeok's collar. The speech above uses the Compression translation strategy, namely translation by condensing meaning. The sentence “너

일로 와 봐” [nô illo wa bwa] literally can be interpreted as 'you, try to come here'. The sentence is translated into 'come here' which has condensed meaning with the reduction of the lexical "you" and "try" in the translation results so that the sentence is more concise.

	Data 2 (Min 16:13)
BSu	아줌마, 여기 천 원어치만더 주세요
	:
	[ajumma, yôgi chônwonôchiman dô juseyo]
BSa	Ma'am, I'd like an extra 1,000 won

The utterance above is an imperative speech act characterized by the existence of an imperative ending in polite informal language -

아요/어요[ayo/ôyo] attached to the phrase 주세요[juseyo] and the context at the time of speech happen. The context of the speech above is as follows. The speech was spoken by Gi Hun to the tteokpokki seller. He asked the seller to increase the amount of food for 1000 Won. The utterances above are translated using the Compression translation strategy, namely translation by condensing meaning. This utterance can literally be interpreted as 'ma'am, just give me another 1,000 Won here'. The utterance is translated as 'ma'am, I want an additional 1,000 won' which has condensed meaning so that it is more concise and easy to understand.

Furthermore, most translation strategy is the literal strategy which is used 24 times. This strategy is also widely used considering that this strategy is the most basic translation strategy and the easiest to do. Based on the analysis, the Literal strategy is mostly used for word-level translation, in other words it is used to translate vocabulary with simple meanings. This is different from compression where most of the translation is at the sentence level (as many as 19 times) because the use of literal strategies especially for sentences will actually lead to unnatural and difficult to understand translation meanings. The following is an example of using the literal strategy in translating imperative speech acts.

Data 3 (Min 9:08)

BSu	저 새끼 잡아!
	[jô saekki jaba!]
BSa	Catch that bastard!

The utterance above is an imperative speech act characterized by an imperative ending of the informal language variety 아/어[a/ô] which attached to the word 잡아[jaba] and the context

when the speech occurs. The context of the speech above is as follows. The speech uttered by one of the thugs while chasing Seong Gi Hun. Each word in the above utterance is translated literally based on its lexical meaning.

Data 4 (Min 16:48)

BSu	가영아 1, 내려
	Ga Yeong
BSa	come on down

The utterance above is an imperative speech act marked with an imperative ending variety of informal language 아/어[a/ô] which attached to the phrase 내려[naeryô] and the context when the speech occurs. The context of the speech above is as follows. Speech uttered by Mrs. Ga Yeong. At that time, Gi Hun was taking Ga Yeong to his mother. Gi Hun carried Ga Yeong behind his back and when they arrived in front of the apartment where his ex-wife lived, Mrs. Ga Yeong immediately told Ga Yeong to get down and enter immediately. The utterances above are translated using a literal translation strategy, namely translation according to its literal meaning. Each word in the above utterance is translated using a literal translation strategy, namely translation according to its literal meaning so that the utterance is translated at the word level into 'Ga Yeong, come on down'.

The third most common type of translation strategy is the Addition Strategy, which is 17 times. This strategy was carried out quite a lot, especially to clarify personal pronouns (as many as 11 times), bearing in mind that in Korean possessive pronouns and personal pronouns are often omitted, whereas in Indonesian removing personal pronouns can make the translation result unnatural. The following is an example of using the addition strategy in translating imperative speech acts.

Data 5 (Min 23:34)

BSu	연락 주십시오
	[yôllak jusipsio]
BSa	Contact (me)

The utterance above is an imperative speech act marked by the presence of an imperative ending in a variety of formal languages

(으)십시오[(eu)sipsio] attached to the word 주십시오[jusipsio]. Context of speech in above is as follows. The story occurs when the mysterious man says that Gi Hun can get more money by playing a game similar to the game he did before for a few days. The mysterious man also gave a business card and said to contact him because there were not many participants left to play the game. Overall, SL can be interpreted as "contact" in TL. However, in TL, there is an addition of the word "I". Addition strategy, translation by adding lexical or words without adding meaning in SL, is used in the speech. The addition of the personal pronoun is only to clarify the object of speech, namely the mysterious man, without adding to the intent of the speech.

Data 6 (Min 32:50)

BSu	말 시키지 마라
	[mal sikhiji mara]
BSa	Don't ask (me) to talk

The utterance above is an imperative speech act marked by the existence of an imperative ending with an equivalent language variety - 어라/아라[ôra/ara] attached to the phrase 시키지 마라[sikhiji mara]. Speech context above are as follows. The speech uttered by participant number 1 to Gi Hun at the game arena building. At that time Gi Hun was shocked because one of the game participants was a grandfather who was very old so Gi Hun wanted to talk to him. However, the old man was trying to count the number of participants who would be participating in the game so he asked Gi Hun not to make him talk because he would disturbing his concentration. The speech above is translated using the Compression and Addition strategy. The utterance above can literally be interpreted as 'don't make it talk'. Speech translates to 'don't talk to me'. The addition strategy is found in the affix "-ku" in the translation results. The addition of the personal pronoun is only to clarify the object of the conversation, namely the speaker himself without adding to the meaning in the speech.

V. CONCLUSION

The most dominant translation strategy used is the Compression strategy. This is in line with Lina Ho's opinion where subtitling must use language that is short, concise, and precise in meaning because in watching a film, of course, there are many scenes or scenes that change quickly so that the audience must be fast in reading and understanding subtitle texts. With this, it is necessary to condense the meaning in the translation results displayed on the subtitles so that the most widely used strategy is the compression strategy.

For further research, it is expected to be able to use other objects of study such as novels, poetry, films, etc. In addition, in researching translation strategies, further research can also use other types of speech and other language hierarchies such as words, phrases, and sentences as research subjects. The choice of different translation strategy theories in research can also provide new references to readers. Researchers also hope that the results of this study can help Korean language learners, teachers, and the general public in understanding translation techniques or strategies, and can even be a reference for further research in analyzing the accuracy of translation..

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